

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN TRADITIONAL AND INCREDIBLE INDIA

Ms. Charan Jeet Singh (Research Scholar)

Dr. Yogender Chouhan

Sunrise University, Alwar, India

ABSTRACT

Women, traditionally have been playing a crucial role in the family as well as in the farm, shop, factory and in the society, but their contribution has not been duly acknowledged. The involvement and participation in the process of development is sine-qua-non for the uplift of women to boost their status in the society. In the present age of globalization where each and every economy of the world is giving emphasis on women empowerment which is not possible by creating employment opportunities for them but to motivate them to go for creating their own enterprise. Women have undergone a radical transformation from merely a homemaker to a dynamic multifaceted personality contributing to the socio-economic growth worldwide. Therefore, a move from family management to enterprise management may be easier than a move from paid employment to self employment.

Key Words: Transparency, Participation, Empowerment

Introduction

During the Vedic period, women's progress kept pace with that of men. Women were men's friends and co-workers. In that action-oriented society, no religious rites could be performed by a man without the participation of his wife. Role played like a daughter, wife and mother by her father, husband and son respectively.

In medieval period, the position of Indian women was very miserable. Women could marry once among Hindus while a man was permitted to have more than one wife. Women were mostly required to live within the premises of their houses to cook food and to feed and take care of their children and other members of the family. Hindu women had no right to inherit property, nor did they enjoy the right to terminate an undesirable marriage (Saheb Deen Maurya ,1988). women were economically and socially, totally dependent on men. This period is known as the darkest period for women in Indian history (Beena Shah.1995).

In the latter half of the eighteenth century, the position of Indian women had reached the greatest degree of deterioration. The social institutions and customs not only thwarted the free growth of women but also regarded them unfit for participation in social, political and religious functions of any significance. They were even debarred from receiving education. Thus for about 2000 years (from 200BC to 1800AD) the position of women was deteriorating (ibid.).

[Charan & Yogender \(2018\) Women Empowerment in Traditional and Incredible India](#)

After British ruled in India, they established the modern capitalist economic system and modern state based on principles of liberty and equality and generated a new climate to bring changes in the old, traditional feudal, un-egalitarian social structure and norms based on equality. They favoured and encouraged education for women.

Independence reinforced the challenges and struggles to improve the status of women. The need to encourage education for women in general and higher education in particular has been recognized in free India. But the improvement in the status of women and their education is not commensurate with expansion in the facilities and opportunities for their education. Women's position changed as the social structure changed from communal to matriarchal and from matriarchal to patriarchal.

The 1991 census counted 407.1 million females against a total population of 846.3 million out of which 297.8 million women live in the rural areas and 27 per cent of the rural women live below the poverty line. It has been established that women are productive workers and integral to India's national economy and make up one third of the country's labour force. Also it has been understood that the poorer the family, the greater the dependence on women's economic productivity. This goes on to prove that enhancing women's economic productivity is an important strategy for improving the welfare of 60 million Indian households below the poverty line.

The literacy status in India, according to the 1991 census stands at 52.21 per cent - males 64.13 per cent and females 39.29 per cent (Government of India, 1991-'92). The level of literacy among rural women is lower than that of the urban women. In some states like Rajasthan female literacy is as low as 20.44 per cent. Although the literacy percentage has shown a steady increase over the last several decades it is still far from the desired standards.

It has also been seen that there is a significant gap between women's (especially rural women's) potential and actual productivity and that the productivity gap of the poor women is much wider than that of poor men. Therefore, women will gain proportionately more, if investment allocation and development efforts are shifted in their favour. Studies have also shown that women's earnings have a positive correlation with children's health, nutrition levels and education and that Indian women contribute a much larger share of their earnings to basic family maintenance than men. Increase in women's income therefore translates more directly into better health and nutrition for children and therefore improving women's productivity, income and quality of life, implies a multifaceted contribution to overall growth and development.

The report by the National Committee on the Status of Women reveals that women's participation in the economy has been declining since 1921. The reasons for the decline of women's participation in the work force differ in urban and rural areas and in rural areas there is a strongly rooted view that the wife's leisure might be regarded as a sign of status by others. The other factors that inhibit women's employment are heavy domestic work load, lack of assumed work, irregular and underpayment of wages, absence of transport facilities, lack of child care centres and other supportive structures.

Today, more and more women are seeking economic opportunity and self determination through enterprise creation and are well prepared to grab the opportunities of the multi-polar world. But at the same time they have to face a number of challenges which are required to be solved by making them and their family aware and attracting financial and moral support in this regard.

Poverty and unemployment are the major problems of any under developed countries, to which India is no exception. In India, at the end of ninth five year span 26.1% of the population was living below poverty line. In the rural area 27.1% of the population was living under poverty. The overall unemployment rate is estimated to 7.32%. The female unemployment rate is 8.5%. The rate of growth of women unemployment in the rural area is 9.8%. Present Indian Rural woman share in agri and rural based activities are:

Activity Percent share by woman

- Ploughing 30%
- Planting 50%
- Livestock 50%
- Harvesting 60%
- Weeding 70%
- Processing and storing crops 85%
- Domestic work 95%

Employment and Labour force

The discrimination against women is clearly seen in the employment opportunities available to them. Besides this social and economic factors are also responsible for the low participation rate for women in the nation's labour force.

According to Leelamma Devasia and V.V. Devasia (1994) the major reasons for this may be:

- Segmentation of labour market which works against women.
- Adverse implications of technological growth for women.
- Lack of unionisation of women workers.
- Absence of purposeful human resource development policy aimed at improving women's employability and productivity through training.
- Conceptual ambiguities and lack of National Labour Policy encompassing workers in organised sector.

As per the 1991 census, work participation rate of women is 23 per cent - 27 per cent for rural women. 19 per cent of the total female work force consists of unpaid family workers. 94 per cent of the total women workers are concentrated in the informal sector, low skills, low status and poor pay.

Andiappen (1980) views that a government can adversely affect the employment rights of women in 4 ways:

- Discrimination in education and training,
- Discrimination in public employment,
- Failing to implement policies requiring fair employment and
- Family laws which deprive women of equal property and other rights.

Even many of the educated women fail to get jobs because they belong to the weaker sex and many others who are employed complain that they are unnecessarily harassed in their offices. The illiterate and poor women who do low grade jobs to earn their livelihood are subjected to several types of abuses and are also generally offered very low wages. Women seek work for many of the same reasons as men: it provides income, fringe benefits, social interactions and a sense of accomplishment (Victor R. Fuchs, 1998).

Working women, both educated and uneducated, are denied equality and justice in their houses as well as in their work places. A working woman who is also a mother, is expected not only to do her office work, but also all the household work, both in the morning and in the evening. She has to do her traditional duties as the wife, mother and the daughter-in-law. She has to labour

hard both in the office and at home. The husband is also not expected to help her and ease her burden. In many a case even if the woman has a white-collar job she is not allowed adequate freedom of movement outside the house and a large number of employed women have few rights over their earnings. A woman also has no legal right over children and she cannot be the guardian of her children so long as her husband is alive (Baral and Kumudini Patnaik, 1990).

Women are denied opportunities to participate in the decision making process. Even when the decisions are to affect their well-being, they are only passive observers. The primary challenge facing women today is to increase their participation so that they get hold of the situation and become actively involved the process of decision making (Chandra, 1997).

Women and Education

Lack of formal as well as informal education for women has a crucial effect on their involvement and status in society. This shortfall is mainly due to the poor appreciation of the value of female education by parents and society in general. There is a false assumption in some sections of rural society that investment in training women/girls is a waste as they ultimately marry and take away the skills acquired to their new families.

Educating women will not only enable them to get better jobs, and even be economically self-sufficient or independent, but also society, as a whole will gain. Women will get married at an older age, choose to have smaller families and in turn nurture and educate their young.

The National Policy on Education 1986 has emphasised that women's development is essential for national development. Its highlights are as given below:

"Education will be used as an agent of basic change in the status of women. In order to neutralize the accumulated distortions of the past, there will be a well-conceived edge in favour of women.

The position of women in respect to education is equal to that of men so far as formal situation is concerned but the structure of society does not allow all the women to benefit by the constitutional provision (Sneha Joshi ,1992).

To quote from the Report of Education commission 1864-66, "For full development of our human resources, the improvement of homes and for moulding the character of children during the most impressionable years of infancy, the education of women is of even greater importance than that of men. In the modern world, the role of women goes much beyond home and the bringing up of the children.

Of the 1.3 billion people who live in absolute poverty around the globe, 70 percent are women. For these women, poverty doesn't just mean scarcity and want. It means rights denied, opportunities curtailed and voices silenced. Consider the following:

- Women work two-thirds of the world's working hours, according to the United Nations Millennium Campaign to halve world poverty by the year 2015. The overwhelming majority of the labor that sustains life – growing food, cooking, raising children, caring for the elderly, maintaining a house, hauling water – is done by women, and universally this work is accorded low status and no pay. The ceaseless cycle of labor rarely shows up in economic analyses of a society's production and value.
- Women earn only 10 percent of the world's income. Where women work for money, they may be limited to a set of jobs deemed suitable for women – invariably low-pay, low-status positions.
- Women own less than 1 percent of the world's property. Where laws or customs prevent women from owning land or other productive assets, from getting loans or credit, or from having the right to inheritance or to own their home, they have no assets to leverage for economic stability and cannot invest in their own or their children's futures.
- Women make up two-thirds of the estimated 876 million adults worldwide who cannot read or write; and girls make up 60 percent of the 77 million children not attending primary school. Education is among the most important drivers of human development: women who are educated have fewer children than those who are denied schooling (some studies correlate each additional year of education with a 10 percent drop in fertility). They delay their first pregnancies, have healthier children (each additional year of schooling a woman has is associated with a 5 to 10 percent decline in child deaths, according to the United Nations Population Fund) and are far more likely to send their own children to school. Yet where women do not have the discretionary income to invest in their own or their children's education, where girls' education is considered frivolous, and where girls are relied on to contribute labor to the household, they miss this unparalleled opportunity to develop their minds and spirits. Their countries suffer too: the World Bank estimates that nations in South Asia and Africa lose .5 to 1 percent growth in per-capita income per year compared to similar countries where children have greater access to quality, basic education. In many societies around the world, women never belong wholly to themselves; they are the property of others throughout their lives.

Their physical well-being – health, security and bodily integrity – is often beyond their own control. Where women have no control over money, they cannot choose to get health care for themselves or their children. Where having a large number of children confers status on both men and women – indeed, where childbearing may be the only marker of value available to women – frequent pregnancy and labor can be deadly. World Health Organization data indicates that in Afghanistan and Sierra Leone, for example, a woman's lifetime chance of dying in childbirth is one in seven; in the United States it is one in 3,418, and in Norway and Switzerland, one in 7,300. In any given year, 15 percent of all pregnant women will face a life-threatening complication, and more than 500,000 – 99 percent of them in the developing world – will die.

Some 130 million girls and women, mostly in sub-Saharan Africa, have been subjected to genital cutting at the behest of their parents, and 2 million more face the blade every year, according to the United Nations Population Fund. Around the globe, home and community are not safe havens for a billion girls and women: At least one in three females on earth has been physically or sexually abused, often repeatedly and often by a relative or acquaintance. By the World Bank's estimate, violence rivals cancer as a cause of morbidity and mortality for women of childbearing age. Even within marriage, women may not be able to negotiate when and what type of sex to have, nor to protest their husbands' multiple sex partners. Poverty and exclusion push some girls and women to engage in sex work, almost always the desperate, last choice of people without other choices. Further, the U.S. Department of State indicates that up to 800,000 people are trafficked across international borders annually: 80 percent of these are women and girls, and the majority is forced into the sex trade. And in the midst of conflict and natural disaster in countries around the world, women's risk of violence skyrockets. Systematic rape as a weapon of war has left millions of girls and women traumatized, forcibly impregnated, and/or HIV positive. These factors combined explain why today more women than men around the world are HIV positive. In sub-Saharan Africa, more than twice as many young women as young men are living with HIV, according to the International Labor Organization. In Lesotho, an old adage says, "A woman is the child of her father, her husband and her son." The constitution treats women as minors, incapable of making decisions... Within the law, households [that do not have a "permanent" male in them] do not exist, which makes women even more vulnerable. Which aspects of women's poverty, their lesser economic, legal and social status, are due to **sex** (the physical attributes and processes mandated by the cellular presence of XX or XY chromosomes), and which to **gender** (the economic, social and cultural attributes and opportunities that human societies have attached to being a woman or a man)? Gender differences pattern our identities, attitudes, roles, relationships and resources more deeply and persistently than class, race or other social constructs. In all societies, including our own, sex and gender are so tightly linked that we have great difficulty disassociating them. Gender roles perpetuated over time and space are normalized: they come to seem as much the natural order as sex differences. Helping women and men uncover and uproot the profoundly unjust gender norms that keep so many women mired in poverty and bereft of dignity is surely CARE's most challenging undertaking to date.

Women's Empowerment

Empowerment refers to increase the spiritual, political, social, or economical strength of individuals and communities. It often involves the empower has to develop confidence in their own capacities.

Human freedom: Expanding human freedom entails expanding human liberties, opportunities, and capabilities. Deprivations in human freedom entail not only the denial of civil and political liberties, but also are associated with hunger, poverty, untreated illnesses, and premature

mortality. A human rights perspective highlights the importance of processes and policies that expand human freedoms and capabilities by respecting, protecting, and fulfilling individual choices and enabling people to achieve what they value.

Universalism and equality: Human rights are inclusive in character and apply to all people everywhere on an equal basis. This principle recognizes the equal dignity and worth of all human beings. All people should be treated fairly and in a consistent and equitable manner.

The multi-dimensional character of well-being: Human rights for the life, survival, integrity, and development of the person include rights to liberty, security, and well-being. These rights reflect the principles of interdependence and indivisibility in the sense that achievement of all human rights should be given equal priority and urgent consideration.

Transparency, participation, and empowerment: In order to expand freedoms and capabilities, development processes and policies must respect human rights and entitlements. The principles of transparency, participation, and empowerment can help to ensure that development institutions are responsible and accountable, and that people are fully informed, influential, and vested in the decision-making processes that affect their lives.

Responsibility and accountability: Individuals, organizations, and governments have responsibilities to respect, promote, and fulfill all human rights for all. Governments have particular responsibilities and are accountable for respecting, promoting, and fulfilling internationally recognized human rights obligations. (*Source:* Moser and Norton 2001.)

WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT: Different dimensional definitions:

Woman empowerment is a reality of women's lives. What, then, is women's empowerment? Women's empowerment has five components: women's sense of self-worth; their right to have and to determine choices; their right to have access to opportunities and resources; their right to have the power to control their own lives, both within and outside the home; and their ability to influence the direction of social change to create a more just social and economic order, nationally and internationally.

Definitions and studies on women empowerment Staples (1990) defined the term 'empowerment' as (1) To gain power (2) To develop power (3) To take/seize power (4) To facilitate/enable power (5) To give/grant power. Papa (1991) explained that "Empowerment of women is nothing but strengthening of their innate vitality". It is humanization of humanity. It can be done through acquiring knowledge, power and experience. It is a sense of internal strength and confidence to face life, the right to determine choices in life and the ability to influence a social process that affects their lives.

Empowerment: Definitions and Meanings economic outcomes. The severance between the private and the public has reinforced the view that citizens, as individuals, or as residents in a community, are not capable of effecting a change in politics or the economy: they are busy realizing personal goals and are involved in conflicts with one another for the sake of their own interests. Self-interest is natural (Perloff, 1987), and this implies that for people to cooperate and contribute to the general interest there needs to be a great change in behavior, attitudes, and human nature. Empowerment is a political concept because it comes out against these views, and connects the individual with a public, a community, and with politics. Individual empowerment is a political demand by women – and men – not to stop them at the door of their residences (Ackelsberg, 1988).

Empowerment promotes involvement in politics because it broadens a person's social understanding and connects her various levels of the empowerment process or its outcomes. Beyond this, the hidden message in the personality constructs is that an empowered person has changed with others in the same situation; empowerment broadens a person's horizons, imbues him with faith in social change, and accords him the ability to change.

Empowerment: Definitions and Meanings social influences operating in the selected environments can contribute to personal development by the interests and competencies they cultivate and the social opportunities they provide, which subsequently shape their possibilities of development (Bandura, 1989, 1997). The connection between the self-efficacy mechanism and the empowerment process is so clear that there can be no doubt about the value of integration between them. The psychological constructs are not the subject of this book, for if we assume that every powerless person needs empowerment, and that potential empowerment exists in every person, then personality qualities are not essential for an understanding of the psychologically in ways that only professionals can understand and measure. Such a message contradicts empowerment language, which calls for equal and transparent relations between professionals (including researchers) and the people in whose lives they intervene (Rappaport, 1985). I recommend that as part of adopting an empowering professional practice we should avoid using concepts which brand people in advance. Since empowerment is not a particular quality of a person, but an important condition for his existence, its realization must correspond to the most diverse theoretically, at least, the infinite) number of human variations. Paradoxically, this very complexity is what enables the process to harmoniously absorb a vast quantity of psychological constructs (Zimmerman, 1995). Although we cannot dismiss the attempt to make connections between psychological theories and the concept of empowerment, my preference is to develop empowerment in a less psychological and more social direction.

A person's empowerment involves her ability to acquire knowledge and skills in order to influence and control her life, and to be an active partner in the lives of others for whom she cares. The need for empowerment of professionals stems from the apprehension that they will not succeed in encouraging empowerment of others from a position of submission and

humiliation. The claim is that a person who does not implement empowerment in her own life will not be able to encourage this process in others. Teachers, for example, have to be intellectuals who use knowledge and information to guide pupils to think, not technicians who transmit knowledge. Today the education system isolates teachers, limits them with regulations and instructions, and does not enable them to use their knowledge in the selection and disposition of study material. A teacher who is treated as a person who is incapable of making a mature decision cannot prepare others for maturity; if she is closely supervised and is not trusted, she will not be able to teach others what autonomy and trust are. Teachers are expected to teach how to take risks, to consider alternatives and to form alliances, while they themselves are limited to technical and mechanical aspects of their profession (Giroux, 1987). For professionals to be able to teach clients how to form alliances, set up coalitions, overcome organizational obstacles and act in a political way, they must first experience all these themselves (Pinderhughes, 1983). Practitioners implement empowerment in their relations with clients, but are captive within a conception of equality that denies the existence of power relations (and of inequality) in their connection with their clients (Hasenfeld, 1987; Hopps et al., 1994). Besides this contradiction, the organization greatly limits their power as autonomous professionals. The responses of powerless employees are characterized by various forms of withdrawal, ineffectiveness, burnout, and leaving the service. The empowering solution proposed is a mutual support group as a means of self-empowerment.

Individual Empowerment The personality structure, as we know, is significantly influenced by environmental conditions. A person is not formed only by heredity and conditions of growth and care, but also by opportunities and experiences in the world around him. Among these, especially important to us is the ability to make decisions and to act in order to attain goals. This ability (or its absence) shapes the person's character and influences the degree to which she will be the effective actor in her life (Pinderhughes, 1983).

Empowerment is an interactive process which occurs between the individual and his environment, in the course of which the sense of the self as worthless changes into an acceptance of the self as an assertive citizen with sociopolitical ability. The outcome of the process is skills, based on insights and abilities, the essential features of which are a critical political consciousness, an ability to participate with others, a capacity to cope with frustrations and to struggle for influence over the environment (Kieffer, 1984).

The process of empowerment is an active process. Its form is determined by the circumstances and the events, but it's Empowerment and Community Planning essence is human activity in the direction of change from a passive state to an active one. The process brings about an integration of self-acceptance and self-confidence, social and political understanding, and a personal ability to take a significant part in decision-making and in control over resources in the environment.

The sense of personal ability connects with civic commitment. Individual empowerment is an expression on the individual level of a multi-leveled process which may be applied to organizations, communities, and social policy (Zimmerman & Rappaport, 1988).

Empowerment is a process of internal and external change. The internal process is the person's sense or belief in her ability to make decisions and to solve her own problems. The external change finds expression in the ability to act and to implement the practical knowledge, the information; the skills, the capabilities and the other new resources acquired in the course of the process (Parsons, 1988). Some writers call the internal change psychological empowerment and the external change political empowerment. According to this distinction, psychological empowerment occurs on the level of a person's consciousness and sensations, while political empowerment is a real change which enables a person to take part in the making of decisions that affect his life. To achieve psychological empowerment a person requires only internal strengths, while to realize his political personal empowerment a person requires environmental conditions, mainly organizational ones, which will enable him to exercise new abilities (Gruber & Trickett, 1987).

In this discussion I do not intend to deal with the practical and the psychological processes of empowerment and the differences between them; rather, I want to emphasize the need for an integration of both. While the traditional approach sees political power as the possession of sufficient influence or authority to bring about a change, or even to impose it, the idea of empowerment adopts a different approach to power, one that does not attribute possession of power to anyone. When power is not conceived as a resource or a concrete.

The critique of locus of control sees it as a culture-dependent concept, which discriminates against those who are in a social and cultural state of powerlessness and lack of control. The locus of control research in fact presupposes that the researchers themselves have an internal locus, and attributes an external locus of control to certain especially weak population groups. If so, it is preferable to see this construct as an indicator of the social situation of those population groups, instead of using it to measure the personality of individuals (Antonovsky, 1979). Self-efficacy (Bandura, 1989) is a central and ongoing individual mechanism (which operates by means of cognitive, motivational and affective processes) which is comprised of a person's perceived belief in her capability to exercise control over events. Studies indicate that a person's belief in her ability to achieve outcomes is, among other things, connected to her thinking patterns—to what extent they help or hinder her to realize goals. This belief determines how a person will judge her situation, and influences the degree of motivation that people mobilize and sustain in given tasks, their degree of endurance in situations of stress and their vulnerability to depression, and the activities and the environmental frameworks that people choose.

Principles Guiding Empowerment Practice The principles of action that stem from the values of empowerment are not rules which determine specifically what the professional should do, but guidelines for selecting suitable practices.

1. Empowerment has to be a permanent component in any problem-solving process, irrespective of the theoretical approach that shapes this process. As a meta-practice, it can and must be integrated into every kind of professional thinking, irrespective of the sort of program or the methods exercised. (Rose & Black, 1985).
2. Giving help. Those who receive help need to be able to give help as well. Hence, as already noted, self-help groups are considered as distinctive promoters of empowerment. Active participation in programs is an
- 16
2. Empowerment and Community Planning empowering principle, and to achieve this it is worth causing a deliberate under-manning of social frameworks (Rappaport, 1985). This means the implementation of programs without sufficient salaried manning of various functions, a situation that mobilizes participants in the program to perform these functions. Frameworks which operate in this way foster empowerment efficiently, because it is essential for the people to help not only as consumers but as people who care for the organization's operation. They enter naturally into a position of worth, and concurrently receive professional and social support with their problems while they perform their valuable role as helpers. Manning of important functions in a program by those using it emphasizes a corollary principle, one that is accepted in community work and essential to the empowerment process: the professional must see his role as temporary. As he encourages empowerment, he also works towards a diminution of his professional presence. He trains leaders local functionaries to take their positions as soon as possible, so that they can take responsibility and be less in need of outside help.
1. Lack of power cannot be compensated for by means which increase lack of power. Economic dependence, which is one of the forms of powerlessness, cannot be improved by means of a program that humiliates and oppresses those in need of it. Hence, an empowering professional ascribes the same importance to the means of activating social programs as to their objectives (at the same time, it is necessary to be cautious and to avoid programs where the means are strongly emphasized but the goals are unimportant).
2. Think big and act small. An important principle in empowerment is to analyze phenomena on the macro level, but to intervene with attention to the micro level. Empowerment demands simultaneous concern for the environment, the collective, its organization and the
3. The collective is a central principle of the empowerment process. Even when the objective is individual the means are collective. Collectivity provides a true rationale for empowerment (Staples, 1990); if the empowerment process were solely individual, it

would have no social significance. Collectivity is the source of the synergy in the process, because it grows in power and extends the boundaries of its influence.

1. Empowerment is a multi-leveled concept. It integrates individuals, groups, organizations, communities and states, as well as contexts—the environmental, cultural, and historical contexts. The influence that each of the levels of empowerment radiates upon all the other levels is of much importance. The principle of levels leads to the conclusion that we should aspire to a policy of empowerment, and to the conjecture that professionals need empowerment in order to be able to empower people who need their help (Rappaport, 1987). Principles Guiding the Relationship between Practitioners and the People Who Need Their Help Empowerment requires a re-examination of the whole of social public policy, and demands of the practitioner a re-examination of the professional relationship.
 - Different people require different solutions for the same problems. In order to arrive at a variety of solutions we must emphasize the strengths of those in need of help, and to use a mixture of resources: of the practitioners and of those who come for help (Solomon, 1985).
 - Cooperation between the helpers and the helped is essential to the empowerment process. The helped bring a distinctive knowledge about their lives and their own point of view about their problems, and the helpers bring specialized knowledge that stems from formal training.
 - Respect for people is the basis for professional relationships. Respect is expressed in treating the request for help not as a sign of weakness or dependence, but as an expression of a need to receive professional service. Respect expresses itself in accepting people's interpretation of reality. Respect for a person and recognition of his strengths confirm his very existence and give it validity. Powerless people tend to cast doubt on the existence of reality as they perceive it. The low self-image of vulnerable people, which involves doubt and self-denial, serves the existing order. People are willing to accept the problems they suffer from as justified, thus reinforcing the negative opinions prevalent about them (Mullender & Ward, 1985; Rose & Black, 1991).
 - Empowerment has a language of its own that influences immediate communication and the meta-communication level. It prefers clarity and simplicity of expression and is very wary of using professional jargon. For example, practitioners who use and think in terms of concepts such as the placebo effect and spontaneous remission contradict messages of empowerment, because they express a lack of faith in people's ability to help themselves outside the professional context (Rappaport, 1985, 1987). Principles Guiding the Design of Social Programs The quality of social programs is critical in determining people's destiny. In the connection between people in need of professional help.

Women and Empowerment

Empowerment is the process of enhancing the capacity of individuals or groups to make choices and to transform those choices into desired actions and outcomes. Central to this process are actions which both build individual and collective assets, and improve the efficiency and fairness of the organizational and institutional context which govern the use of these assets.

The most conspicuous feature of the term empowerment is that it contains the word 'power'. It may be broadly defined as control over material assets, intellectual resources and ideology.

The process of challenging existing power relations and of gaining great control over the sources of power may be termed as empowerment. Empowerment in its simplest form means the manifestation of redistribution of power that challenges patriarchal ideology and the male dominance (Chandra, 1997).

It is both a process and the result of the process. Empowerment represents a means for accomplishing community development tasks and can be conceptualized as involving two key elements: giving community members the authority to make decisions and choices and facilitating the development of the knowledge and resources necessary to exercise these choices (Zippy, 1995).

Robert Adams (1990) defines empowerment as the process by which individuals, groups and or communities become able to take control of their circumstances and achieve their own goals, thereby being able to work towards maximising the quality of their lives.

The term empowerment refers to a range of activities from individual self-assertion to collective resistance, protest and mobilization that challenges basic power relations (Kumud Sharma ,1991-'92).

For individuals and groups where class, caste, ethnicity and gender determine their access to resources and power, their empowerment begins when they not only recognise the systematic forces that oppress them, but also act to change existing power relationships.

Conclusions:

Empowerment commonly means 'becoming powerful: self help may thus be viewed as one form of empowerment. Empowerment may be used to mean simply "enablement" (Robert Adams, 1990).

According to Kumud Sharma (1991-'92) empowerment is a process aimed at changing the nature and direction of systematic forces which marginalise women and other disadvantaged sections in a given context.

Empowerment is also visualized as an enabling process. The process of empowerment operates at all the levels of the individual, group, family, organisation and community and also in the different aspects of people's lives. For example, one person may feel empowered because of something realised or understood; another may experience empowerment once a new job, course or career opportunity is achieved.

Empowerment in its multiple forms continues to be the dominant requirement of all grass root level situations. (Ram Rajput and Hem Lata Swarup , 1994)

Empowerment implies fundamental redistribution of power within and between families/societies. It is an externally induced process of change towards women's equality and development. It is a process of equity enhancement and can be achieved only through disempowering some structures, systems and institutions. The process is often selective and uneven. Here power is used not as a mode of domination but as strength, ability to influence social and political processes, the right to choose and the ability to influence the direction of social change.

Empowering is development of skills and abilities of people to enable them to manage better development delivery systems. Some see it as more fundamental and as essentially concerned with enabling people to decide upon and undertake actions which they believe are essential to their development (Marina Pinto, 1995).

The empowerment process encompasses several mutually reinforcing components but begins with and is supported by economic independence which implies access to and control over production resources. A second component of empowerment is knowledge and awareness, the third is self-image and the final component is autonomy.

References

- Amriah, et al. (2015). Women and Liveability: Best Practices of Empowerment from Malaysia. Malaysian Journal of Society and Space. Vol 5 p 26-36.
- Anju Malhotra et al. (2009). Innovation for Women's Empowerment and Gender Equality. International Center for Research on Women.
- Arjun Kumar & Leena Gurung. (2010). An Assessment of Factors Influencing Empowerment Level of Females: A case Study of
- Pohara. Economic Journal of Development. Vol 11&12 No 1-2.

- Arumugam, G.Marthandan&Indra Devi. (2016). Economic Empowerment of Malaysian Women through Entrepreneurship:
- Barriers and Enablers. Asian Social Science.Vol 12 No 6.
- Balraj, S. (2000).Dis-empowering Women on Malaysian TV.Asia Pacific nMedia Educator. P 148-163.
- Esther Duflo. (2012). Women Empowement and Economic Development.Journal of Economic Literature. Vol 50 p 1051-1079.
- Judith Warner. (2014). Women’s Leadership What’s True, What’s False, and Why It Matters. Center for American Progress.
- Kamla Gupta & P.Princy Yesudian.(2006). Evidence of Women’s Empowerment. GeoJournal. P 365-380.
- Natalie& Katie.(2013). Gender Discrimination in the Workplace.Faculty of Social Sciences, California.
- Neha Pandey. (2014). Women Empowerment: Questioning Gender Equality in Cotemporary Society. Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. Volume IV,Issue VI Nov-Dec 2014.
- Rajeshwari, M. (2015).A Study on Issues and Challenges of Women Empowerment.Journal of Business and Management. Vol 4 No 1 p 13-19.
- Rana Haq. (2013). Intersectionality of Gender and other Forms of Identity: Dillemas and Challenges fcing Women in India